

Study of the antioxidant and hepatoprotective activity of the extract from *Gleditsia triacanthos* L. seeds

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Against the background of simulated toxic hepatitis by carbon tetrachloride in rats, a stable form of damage to the hepatobiliary system was obtained. Under these conditions, biochemical analysis of the activity of the studied enzymes, such as ALT, AST, GGT, and alkaline phosphatase, indicates an increase in the activity of transaminases in the blood serum. This situation indicates damage to hepatocyte membranes, an increase in their permeability, as well as the death of some liver cells caused by the introduction of carbon tetrachloride, which is accompanied by the release of intracellular substances into the blood and lymph. Against this background, the use of *G. triacanthos* extract causes a positive trend in changes in enzyme activity. The new agent significantly stimulated the normalization of the biochemical parameters of the blood of animals, while stabilization of aminotransferases and a significant decrease in the level of bilirubin were observed in the body.

Keywords: *Gleditsia triacanthos* L., tetrachloromethane hepatitis model, antioxidant and hepatoprotective effect

INTRODUCTION

Jam, behmez, nutritional supplements, etc., made from the fruits of the carob plant. There is a number of information in the contemporary literature about the ability of the products to be pain-relieving, antibacterial, immunostimulating, against allergies, bronchial asthma, and tumor diseases, as well as to cleanse the liver of toxins (Gasimov et al., 2004; Garayev and Movsumov, 2010; Garayev, 2012; Mammadov et al., 2014; Putyrskiy and Prikhorov, 2005; Samylina and Anosova, 2007). Goat horn fruits (together with their seeds) are ground and mixed with milk and honey and cooked as coffee or made into behemoth and used to strengthen the digestive process, against diarrhea and constipation, to expand the bronchi and against polio (Kerimov et al., 1996, 2010). The use of its fruits together with red radish has a significant positive effect in the treatment of lung cancer. Since the fruits of the plant are very rich in phosphorus and calcium, they are used in the treatment of osteoporosis. There are enough biologically active substances in the germ of the seeds of the carob plant. Taking this into account, using special technological methods, the embryo of the seeds of this plant was separated and alcohol and oil extracts were obtained from it (Taghiyev et al., 2012). The biological activity of the extracts

was studied at the scientific research center of the university.

Objective of the research. Study of the antioxidant and hepatoprotective effect of the extract obtained from the germ of carob seeds.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The main material of the study was the water extract obtained from the germinal part of the seeds of the goat's horn plant (*Gledichia triacanthos* L.) by a special technological method at the Department of Pharmaceutical Technology of AMU (Taghiyev et al., 2012). In order to study the hepatoprotective effect of the extract, an experimental hepatitis model was created in 24 white rats (weight 180-220 g). For this purpose, the rats were kept hungry for one day, then for 2 days, after dissolving 2.6 ml of tetrachloromethane (CCl₄) in 10 ml of vaseline oil, the animals were fed through a special probe with the condition that each rat got 0.5 ml. The creation of an acute hepatitis model in white rats using this method was confirmed by the results of biochemical and histological analyses in previous studies (Khalilov et al., 2017; Akhundov et al., 2018b, 2021). Experimental animals were divided into 4 groups. In the first group, 6 rats (control group) were kept in the vivarium of ETM under normal feeding

and water intake conditions. In the second group, 6 rats with a hepatitis model were kept in the vivarium of ETM under normal feeding and water intake conditions. In the third group, 6 rats were fed with a special tube with 1 ml of water extract obtained from the seeds of Goat horn every day for 10 days (test group). In the fourth group, 6 rats were fed with a 1 ml dose of herbal preparation Silimart Hepa (comparison group) for 10 days. After 10 days, control and experimental animals were anesthetized with 1% hydrochloride lidocaine solution and slaughtered according to accepted rules. Their blood samples were sent to the biochemistry laboratory of ETM for biochemical analysis. The amount of total bilirubin, the activity of alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), gamma-gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT) and alkaline phosphatase (ALP), the amount of lipid peroxidation products - MDA, DC, and the activity of SOD and catalase were determined in the collected blood samples. Enzyme activity was analyzed by the ultraviolet analysis method in the Bioscreen MS-2000 USA machine (Guliyeva et al., 2018). The amount of MDA and DC, and catalase activity were determined by the method (Guliyeva et al., 2020). To determine the antioxidant activity of the water extract obtained from the seeds of the carob plant, 0.1 ml of 0.1% adrenaline hydrochloride solution was added to 2 ml of bicarbonate buffer (pH =10.65), and the optical density (OD) of the mixture was measured for 10 minutes at a thickness of 10 mm. and determined in a spectrophotometer (wavelength 347 nm) in a special cuvette (OD₁). After that, 0.03 ml of carob extract and 0.1 ml of 0.1% adrenaline hydrochloride were added again to 2 ml of bicarbonate buffer (pH=10.65), and the optical density of the mixture was measured in a 10-mm-thick cuvette at a wavelength of 10 minutes. It

was determined in a spectrophotometer at 347 nm (OD₂).

The antioxidant index of the extract was calculated according to the following formula

$$DAI = (OD_1 - OD_2) \cdot 100 / OD_1$$

If the obtained result is more than 10%, the studied extract is considered to have antioxidant capacity (Sirota, 2000).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the *in vitro* determination of the antioxidant capacity of the water extract obtained from the seeds of the goat's horn plant are given in the table below (Table 1). As can be seen from the table, the water extract from the seeds of Goat's horn significantly weakens the autoxidation process of adrenaline *in vivo* starting from the 3rd minute and prevents the formation of reactive oxygen species. At this time, the highest value was observed in the 10th minute (74.6%). It proves that this extract has quite high antioxidant properties (Rice-Evans et al., 1995).

After that, the rats were decapitated according to the accepted rules, and their blood samples were used for biochemical analysis. The results of biochemical analyses showed that the value of blood biochemical indicators (AST, ALT, GGT, GF, MDK, DC, catalase, SOD, etc.) in intact rats was close to the norm (Table 2). However, in the blood of rats with acute hepatitis syndrome, compared to intact cells, AST increased by 40.2%, ALT by 103.7%, GGT by approximately 10 times, GF by 2 times, MDK by 2.5 times, DC by 3 times, catalase decreased by 64.8%, SOD – by 2 times, and total bilirubin increased by 15 times (Table 2).

Table 1. Time-dependent changes in the antioxidant capacity of water extract obtained from carob seeds

Variant	Time (minutes)							
	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
OD ₁	0.239	0.250	0.279	0.302	0.335	0.377	0.396	0.433
OD ₂	0.194	0.176	0.163	0.150	0.141	0.129	0.120	0.110
AOA, %	18.8	29.6	41.6	50.3	57.9	65.8	69.7	74.6

Table 2. Determination of biochemical and lipid peroxidation products in the blood of rats after 10 days of treatment with *Gleditsia triacanthos* L. extract and Silimart Hepa, n=6

Variant	AST (U/L)	ALT (U/L)	GGT (U/L)	GF μmol/l	MDK μmol/l	DC D ₂₃₂ /ml	Catalaze μmol/l	SOD μmol/l	Total bilirubin μmol/l
Intact animals	225.4±4.1	84.3±0.7	1.99±0.2	338.3±6.0	2.31±0.2	0.64±0.1	11.7±0.01	67.6±2.3	1.50±0.01
Hepatitis model was created	316.1±3.9*	171.7±18*	21.8±1.4*	649.3±4.5*	5.53±0.2*	1.9±0.01*	7.1±0.01*	29.5±0.9*	22.5±0.7*
Goat horn	248.7±2.7*	96.3±1.7*	3.8±0.1*	352.2±2.6*	2.31±0.01	0.65±0.1*	11.4±0.2	57.3±1.4*	2.08±0.3*
Silimart Hepa	266.7±1.4	100.2±0.7*	3.9±1.1*	376.5±2.5*	2.48±0.01	0.64±0.02*	11.3±0.1	61.9±1.9*	2.25±0.3*

Accuracy: P<0.05*.

Most of these indicators approached the level of intact animals after 10 days of treatment with Silimart

Hepa and Carob extract in rats with a hepatitis model. Only the value of AST and general knowledge was slightly higher than the norm (Table 2).

As a result of treatment with horsetail extract for 10 days, the activity of ALT, AST, and γ -GTP in the blood was 1.3, respectively, compared to animals with hepatitis syndrome; It decreased by 1.2 and 2.1 times. During the 10-day treatment period, the amount of total bilirubin in the blood decreased by 1.2 times compared to the hepatitis model due to the effect of carob extract. Markers of lipid peroxidation processes and the state of the AOM system were also studied in intact and experimental group rats. The results of biochemical analyses revealed that the amount of MDA and DC in rats exposed to tetrachloromethane increased by 2.4 times and 3.0 times, respectively, compared to intact animals. The activity of catalase and SOD enzymes decreased by 60.7% and 43.6%, respectively (Table 2). When the acute hepatitis model rats were fed with Hepasilimart drug for 10 days, biochemical indicators in the blood decreased: AST - 1.4 times, GGT - 4.8 times, and AF by 1.5 times compared to the tetrachloromethane model group. However, in the animals given Silimart Hepa, these indicators were AST - 7.9%, GGT - 30%, AF - 15% more than the animals that received the goat's horn extract. Compared to the hepatitis model, catalase activity increased by 10.7%, and compared to the control group, it was lower than 4%. Based on the results of the research, it can be concluded that after feeding the horsetail extract to the animals, it is quickly absorbed into the blood, since it contains a large amount of flavonoids (Garayev and Movsumov, 2010; Garayev, 2012), showing antioxidant properties, reducing the glutathione reserve in the liver and therefore, preventing liver damage from the effects of toxins (Akhundov et al., 2018a; Esaulenko, 2014; Kerimov et al., 1996).

CONCLUSIONS

The extract obtained from the seed germ of the carob plant cultivated in the Absheron region has a hepatoprotective effect. A decrease in the activity of ALT, AST, and GF in the blood, a slight increase in the activity of SOD and catalase, and a decrease in the products of lipid peroxidation processes were recorded when the rats with liver pathology were given the extract of the seeds. The obtained results show that goat horn extract has hepatoprotective ability. It can be assumed that the hepatoprotective activity of carob extract is related to the presence of sufficient flavonoids and phenolic acids in its content.

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Keçibuynuzu (*Gleditsia triacanthos* L.) toxumlarından alınmış ekstraktının antioksidant və hepatoprotektor fəallığının öyrənilməsi

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Siçovullarda tetraxlorometan ilə zəhərli hepatitin modelləşdirilməsi fonunda hepatobiliar sistemin stabil zədələnməsi forması əldə edilmişdir. Bu şəraitdə ALT, AST, GGT və qələvi fosfataza kimi tədqiq olunan fermentlərin fəaliyyətinin biokimyəvi analizi qan zərdabında transaminazaların fəallığının artdığını göstərir. Bu vəziyyət hepatosit membranlarının zədələnməsi, onların keçiriciliyinin artması, həmçinin karbon tetraxloridə daxil olması nəticəsində yaranan bəzi qaraciyər hüceyrələrinin ölümünü göstərir, bu da hüceyrədaxili maddələrin qan və limfaya salınması ilə müşayiət olunur. Bunun fonunda keçibuynuzu ekstraktının istifadəsi ferment aktivliyində dəyişikliklərdə müsbət tendensiyaya səbəb olur. Yeni agent heyvanların qanının biokimyəvi parametrlərinin normallaşmasını əhəmiyyətli dərəcədə stimullaşdırdı, eyni zamanda orqanizmdə aminotransferazaların sabitləşməsi və bilirubin səviyyəsinin əhəmiyyətli dərəcədə azalması müşahidə edildi.

Açar sözlər: Keçibuynuzu ekstraktı, tetraxlorometan hepatit modeli, antioksidant və hepatoprotektor təsir